

Ingrid LeGriffon¹, Elise Ruaud¹, Emir Ganić², Tatjana Krstić Simić², Bojana Mirković², Miguel Baena³, David Mocholí³, Marta Alonso³, Cristina Barrado⁴, Jovana Kuljanin⁴

¹ DAAA, ONERA, Institut Polytechnique de Paris, Paris, France

² University of Belgrade, Faculty of Transport and Traffic Engineering, Belgrade, Serbia

³ Nommon Solutions and Technologies, Madrid, Spain

⁴ Polytechnic University of Catalonia, Barcelona, Catalunya, Spain

EVALUATING URBAN AIR MOBILITY NOISE IMPACTS

PROCENA UTICAJA BUKE U OKVIRU URBANE VAZDUŠNE MOBILNOSTI

Abstract - This research introduces a novel methodology for assessing noise pollution caused by Urban Air Mobility (UAM) activities, with a particular emphasis on how these impacts vary across different population segments, including distinctions by age and gender. This study is conducted within the framework of the Horizon Europe MUSE project (Measuring U-Space Social and Environmental Impact), focusing on the development of a performance framework to evaluate the social and environmental impacts of UAM, with an emphasis on noise. Utilizing an innovative simulation toolset, drone-generated noise is modelled and these data are integrated with dynamic population distribution maps, derived from mobile network data and GPS information. For the illustrative purposes, the toolset has been tested on three case studies based in Madrid: evaluating the noise impact of a drone during its cruise phase over residential and downtown areas, assessing the effects of take-off in a residential neighborhood, and examining the cumulative impacts of multiple drone flights. The findings provide crucial insights into the local environmental impacts of UAM and are expected to inform the development of more targeted U-space regulations and strategies for enhancing social acceptance. The outcomes of this research are anticipated to be valuable to a wide range of stakeholders, including ATM experts, regulators, policymakers, urban planners, health officers, environmental health specialists, authorities of European cities and regions, citizens' associations, and many others.

Key words: urban Air Mobility (UAM), drone-generated noise, social acceptance, noise mapping, noise indicators, performance framework

Rezime - Ovo istraživanje predlaže novu metodologiju za procenu zagađenja bukom uzrokovanom aktivnostima urbane vazdušne mobilnosti (UAM), sa posebnim naglaskom na to kako ovi uticaji variraju među različitim segmentima populacije, uključujući razlike po starosnoj dobi i polu. Studija se sprovodi u okviru Horizon Europe MUSE projekta (Measuring U-Space Social and Environmental Impact), fokusirajući se na razvoj okvira za procenu performansi socijalnih i ekoloških uticaja UAM, sa naglaskom na buku. Koristeći inovativan alat za simulaciju, modelovana je buka koju proizvode dronovi i ovi podaci su integrisani sa dinamičkim mapama raspodele populacije, koje su dobijene kombinovanjem podataka mobilnih mreža i GPS informacija. U svrhu ilustracije, skup alata je testiran na tri studije slučaja u Madridu: procena uticaja buke drona tokom faze krstarenja iznad stambenih i centralnih gradskih područja, procena efekata poletanja u stambenoj četvrti, i ispitivanje kumulativnih uticaja više letova dronova. Nalazi pružaju ključne uvide u lokalne ekološke uticaje UAM-a i očekuje se da će doprineti razvoju ciljanijih U-space propisa i strategija za unapređenje društvenog prihvatanja. Rezultati ovog istraživanja mogu biti korisni širokom spektru zainteresovanih strana, uključujući stručnjake za upravljanje vazдушnim saobraćajem (ATM), regulatore, donosiocima politika, urbaniste, zdravstvene službenike, specijaliste za zaštitu životne sredine, vlasti evropskih gradova i regiona, udruženja građana, i mnoge druge.

Ključne reči: urbana vazдушna mobilnost (UAM), buka dronova, društveno prihvatanje, mapiranje buke, indikatori buke, okvir za procenu performansi